

6 Major Ayurvedic Treatments for Insomnia

Before we head on to the [Ayurvedic Treatments for Insomnia](#), it is better to understand the condition that is insomnia and the causes that give birth to this condition. The process of resting and rejuvenating both the mind and the body occurs naturally during sleep. But when they go to bed, a lot of individuals find that they have trouble falling or staying asleep. When some individuals go to bed, they are unable to fall asleep, while others wake up throughout the night and are unable to fall back asleep again. Insomnia is defined as the inability to fall asleep or sleep soundly. The repercussions may be incapacitating and life-changing if they occur after a lengthy period of time during which the condition has been present. In order for our bodies to operate properly, we need to rest.

A sound night's sleep and a good night's rest are essential to maintaining good health, according to Ayurvedic theory. Insomnia may develop, however, if Vata and pitta humours predominate and kapha humour is diminished.

Vata-type insomnia is characterized by difficulty falling asleep, tossing and turning during the night, and waking up feeling more alert than when they went to bed. Pitta-type insomnia affects those who only sleep in fits and starts, or who wake up often in the middle of the night with palpitations, physical discomfort, and mental upheavals including anxiety, rage, and depression.

Reasons Why People Can't Sleep

- An inappropriate diet and an unhealthy lifestyle, both of which may aggravate vata and pitta.
- The consistent use of stimulants such as coffee and tea,
- Food that is too cold, dry, fried, or hot
- Emotions that have been repressed
- Excessive arousal as well as emotional problems such as anxiety, irritability, and overwork

The Ayurvedic Treatment for Insomnia

Ayurvedic treatment for insomnia focuses on re-establishing equilibrium throughout the body and re-establishing the body's natural cycle of sleep and wakefulness. Insomnia is one of the many chronic illnesses that, according to the teachings of Ayurveda, are caused by an accumulation of impurities in the body. Toxins may be produced in our bodies, and our capacity to eliminate them can be hindered by factors such as nutrition, digestion, a lifestyle that is too busy, and stress levels that are too high. Toxins that

have built up in our bodies may mess with our biochemistry and disrupt our metabolism, which can affect our ability to sleep.

When treating insomnia with Ayurveda, an Ayurveda practitioner would use a comprehensive approach to investigate the underlying causes of the patient's inability to fall or stay asleep. Your dosha, food, physical fitness, allergies, mental health, lifestyle, and a lot of other things are all taken into consideration by him or her. After that, the healthcare provider will realize that achieving a state of equilibrium across as many facets of your health and wellness as possible is essential for the treatment of insomnia. Ayurvedic treatments for insomnia are meant to address the underlying reasons for your insomnia; eliminate impurities from the body; improve digestion and metabolism; restore balance to the doshas, and enhance your body's innate capacity to heal itself.

Top 6 Ayurvedic Herbs For Sleeplessness

- Brahmi (*Bacopa monnieri*)
- Shankhapushpi (*Convolvulus pluricaulis*)
- Vacha (*Acorus calamus*)
- Sarpagandha (*Rauvolfia serpentine*)
- Ashwagandha (*Withania somnifera*)
- Jatamansi (*Nardostachys jatamansi*)

Panchakarma for Sleep Disorders

Panchakarma and other related treatments are highly recommended for detoxifying the body and eliminating toxins, both mental and physical, that may cause insomnia. Some treatments are as follows:

Vasti (Medicated Enema)

Sleep issues almost always have some kind of connection to the state of your digestive system. The colon is traditionally thought to be the location of the vata dosha's seat. Colon cleaning with therapeutic herbs helps to restore equilibrium to your vata dosha and lower intestine. This is one of the many benefits of colon cleansing. An expert in Ayurvedic medicine will devise the most effective kind of therapeutic enema for you to use.

Shirodhara:

Because it has such a deeply relaxing effect on the neurological system, shirodhara is a great therapy for insomnia as well as the tension and worry that are associated with it. After around thirty to forty-five minutes of having a stream of warm medicinal oil very

slowly poured into the centre of your forehead (the area of the so-called “third eye”), you will next have a treatment consisting of a light scalp massage and reflexology. Incredible results have been achieved! Shirodhara is a non-invasive therapy that makes it possible to control insomnia without the use of pharmaceuticals. Shirodhara should ideally be experienced multiple times each week for about one month in order to get the greatest outcomes.

Shiroabhyanga (Massage of the Head)

A calming effect on the nervous system may be achieved by the use of therapeutic head massage. During the massage, we will use medicinal oils that have been specifically formulated for your condition and that are easily absorbed by the head, scalp, and hair roots.

Padabhyanga (Massage of the Feet)

Padhabyanga is relaxing, revitalizing, and tranquil. It restores equilibrium to the autonomic nervous system by activating important marma points, hence relieving symptoms of autonomic nervous system dysfunction.

Abhyanga (Body Massage)

The use of medicated oil during a full-body massage during a massage therapy session helps increase blood and lymphatic circulation throughout the body. It may bring about a state of profound calm and contentment in both the body and the mind by bringing the body’s chakras, nadis (energy channels), and marma (energy centers) into harmony.

Practices like yoga and meditation In order to promote restful sleep, Ayurveda recommends practicing calming activities like yoga and meditation.

How Is Management of Insomnia Done Using Ayurveda?

An initial examination by an ayurvedic practitioner is the first step in the ayurvedic treatment of insomnia. During this assessment, your major dosha and any existing imbalances will be determined. Your individual detoxification treatments, herbal regimens, and nutritional strategies are crafted by an expert ayurvedic physician.